

Correlational Effect of ICT Blended Learning Infrastructure on Business Education Students' Academic Performance in Rivers State Tertiary Institutions, Nigeria.

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Abstract

This study investigated the correlational effect of ICT blended learning infrastructure on business education students' academic performance in Rivers State tertiary institutions. The study adopted a descriptive research design with a correlational investigation type. The population of the study comprised of 640 Business Education undergraduates' students (RSU = 6140: IAUE= 6140: FCET = 6140). Simple random sampling technique was used to select 614 students that served as the study respondents. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used in testing the various hypotheses with the help of the Statistical Packages for Social Sciences Version 23.0. The findings revealed existence of significant correlational effect of ICT blended learning infrastructure on business education students' academic performance in Rivers State tertiary institutions. Based on the findings, the study concluded that ICT blended learning infrastructure significantly correlates with business education students' academic performance in Rivers State tertiary institutions. The study recommended that administrators of tertiary institutions in Rivers State should adopt ICT blended learning infrastructure as a strategy to boost students experience, as well as improve overall business education students' academic performance; they should also consider the strategic role of ICT blended learning infrastructure in their quest to understand the causes of students performance, this would boost teacher ratings as well as improve overall performance.

Keywords: ICT Blended Learning Infrastructure, Business Education Students' Academic Performance, Standardized Test Scores, Grade Point Averages, Teacher Ratings.

Introduction

The world has changed tremendously within the past few years. This evolution has given rise to several phenomena, chiefly among these is the concept of information and communication technology (Vo, Zhu & Diep, 2017). Wosu (2023) hints that the advent of ICT has changed the way we do virtually everything. For example, traditional in-person lectures used to be the standard for higher educational teaching and learning but, with ICT, the trajectory has changed as there has been an incredible modification in the educational process (Narad & Abdullah, 2016). Today, a lot of people have described the traditional face-to-face pattern as a method of passive instruction (Cooper, 2018). According to students, in-person instruction is rather dull and does not facilitate group projects, which present difficulties for both students and instructors (Eunice & Linda, 2023). Then, Blended Learning (BL), which blends online and classroom instruction, enters the picture. Additionally, it promotes better educational outcomes targeted at raising students' academic performance and supports both individual and group learning activities (Narad & Abdullah, 2016). The work of Narad & Abdullah (2016) portrayed academic achievement as the result of the learning process and is estimated by the teacher by the use of educational objectives and/or grades

that teachers and students establish in order to be met over a predetermined period of time. As determined by standard test scores, grade point averages, and teacher ratings, Business Education student academic performance describes how well a Business student meets the objectives of a Business course (Bupo & Ibeneme, 2020). The failure or success of any institution is mostly determined by the academic achievement of students in the institution (Narad & Abdullah, 2016). Institutions and academics are currently looking for ways to improve the academic achievement of Rivers State Business students. Agozie (2019) contends that switching from traditional to modern teaching approaches is necessary to improve students' academic achievement. According to Wosu (2023), modern learning methods facilitates the learning process and enable students to understand better. These modern learning methods include the adoption of information and communications technology (ICT) blending learning (Narad & Abdullah, 2016).

Global educational change in recent years has been sparked by the quick development of information and communications technologies (ICTs) (Nichol & Watson, 2003). It enabled a shift for traditional to blended learning environment (Cooper, 2018). ICT Blended Learning infrastructure refers as a combination of information communication technology tools with conventional face-to-face educational method in such a carefully planned pedagogically useful style (Lucia, Takavarasha, & Mubango, 2023). This infrastructure encompasses hardware, software, networks data centres, and other facilities that support both online and face-to-face learning experiences (Narad & Abdullah, 2016). These infrastructures are crucial for academic success. According to Vo *et al* (2017) Blended Learning enhance participant performance in learning.

Scholars (Itam, Abang, Eze, & Takon, 2024; Nayak, Barik, & Bag, 2024; Olatunde-Aiyedun & Adams, 2022; Eunice & Linda, 2023) have argued that ICT-blending infrastructure influences students' academic performance. However, despite the global emphasis on adopting ICT blended infrastructure in education, there is still a growing concern over how it affects the academic performance of student in Rivers State. Also, there is scarcity of literature which investigated the effects of ICT Blended Learning in students' academic achievements in Rivers State. To address this gap, this study was designed to investigate the effect of ICT Blended Learning in students' academic outcomes in Rivers State. By addressing this gap, this research complements the existing bulk of knowledge already available in the field of Education.

Statement of Problem

Cooper (2018) asserted that while the traditional classroom method promotes face-to-face connection between educators and students, it might not take into account each student's unique learning preferences and might not be adaptable enough for self-paced learning. Because students' engagement may be limited to what the teacher allows in class, the traditional classroom method may not be student-centered. These issues can be addressed by adopting ICT Blended Learning infrastructure (Bupo & Ibeneme, 2020). Various empirical studies have been carried out in relation to this study. For instance, Nayak, Barik, and Bag (2024) examined how Blended Learning affected the secondary school students' social science academic performance in Mayurbhanj District's Baripada town. Bupo & Ibeneme (2020) looked at the performance of Business Education students in financial accounting in universities in Rivers State, Nigeria, was affected by the Blended Learning approach. A study by Ashibekong (2020) examined the connection between students' achievements in Business courses and ICT facilities.

Despite the significant role of ICT Blended Learning infrastructure in boosting Business Education student academic performance, there is still a noticeable research gap in investigating the effect of ICT Blended Learning infrastructure and tertiary institutions' Business students' performance in Rivers State. Thus, this study aimed to seal this identified gap via examining the effect of ICT Blended Learning infrastructure and Business students' learning outcome in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this research was to explore the correlational effect of ICT Blended Learning infrastructure on Business Education students' academic performance in Rivers State tertiary institutions. The study sought to accomplish the following particular objectives:

1. Ascertain the correlational effect of ICT Blended Learning infrastructure on standardized test scores in Rivers State tertiary institutions.
2. Ascertain the correlational effect of ICT Blended Learning infrastructure on grade point averages in Rivers State tertiary institutions.
3. Ascertain the correlational effect of ICT Blended Learning infrastructure on teacher ratings in Rivers State tertiary institutions.

Research Questions

The research questions addressed by the study were as follows:

1. To what extent does ICT Blended Learning infrastructure correlate with standardized test scores in Rivers State tertiary institutions?
2. To what extent does ICT Blended Learning infrastructure correlate with grade point averages in Rivers State tertiary institutions?
3. To what extent does ICT Blended Learning infrastructure correlate with teacher ratings in Rivers State tertiary institutions?

Research Hypotheses

This paper tested the underlisted hypotheses:

Ho1: ICT Blended Learning infrastructure does not significantly correlate with standardized test scores in Rivers State tertiary institutions.

Ho2: ICT Blended Learning infrastructure does not significantly correlate with grade point averages in Rivers State tertiary institutions.

Ho3: ICT Blended Learning infrastructure does not significantly correlate with teacher ratings in Rivers State tertiary institutions.

Literature Review

Supplemental Model

In 1973, Dr. Deanna Martin of the University of Missouri–Kansas City created the Supplemental Instruction (SI) model (Vo et al., 2017). SI model, is a peer-assisted academic support program designed to help students in challenging courses. It involves students attending regular study sessions led by trained peer leaders who facilitate collaborative learning (Itam *et al.*, 2024). The

SI model assumes that students learn more effectively when they work together and discuss course material, as peer interactions often promote deeper understanding and retention of information. The Supplemental Instruction (SI) Model can be applied to study the correlational effect of ICT Blended Learning infrastructure on Business Education students' academic performance in Rivers State tertiary institutions by combining peer-assisted learning with modern ICT tools. The goal would be to understand how well this approach enhances academic performance through Blended Learning environments.

Concept of ICT Blended Learning Infrastructure

Computer-assisted instruction has become pivotal to effective teaching and learning in today's world. It is no longer enough to do the face-to-face interaction, the contemporary space demands the integration of various instructional materials and sources to boost learning among students (Itam *et al.*, 2024). Another name for Blended Learning is "hybrid learning." It suggests a carefully thought-out blending of traditional in-person instruction with online learning. To say something is blended means a combination of two on several variables. Therefore, blended education means an educational delivery model in which online education is combined with traditional education method (Wosu, 2023). Blended Learning explains an instructional program that is prepared in the most appropriate way, by combining various learning approaches such as technologies, activities and activity types. The word, "blending" resonates with a fresh method of in-person instruction combined with more electronic resources. ICT-enhanced Blended Learning offers a vast learning method by combining in-class or in-person teaching with ICT usage.

Business Education

In both secondary and tertiary educational institutions, Business Education is a course of study and a component of Vocational Education programs that are intended to give students the academic and practical skills they need for both self-employment as entrepreneurs and salaried work (Cooper, 2018).

Students' Academic Performance

Academic achievement is correlated with the results of a student's education which is reflected in students' knowledge acquisition. It measures how well a student meets educational standards (Itam *et al.*, 2024) Academic performance is evaluated according to objective standards like final course grades and grading point average. It is also assessed through formative and summative assessments.

Standardized Test Scores: A test that has uniform procedures for administration and scoring, so that results from different people can be compared. A test given to different groups of test takers to help equate their scores. The anchor test can be a set of questions that appear in both forms of the test, or it can be a separate test. Standardized tests are designed to be reliable, so that they can be used to compare the performance of large groups of test takers.

Grade Point Averages: implies a numerical summary of a student's academic performance over a period of time, such as a semester or academic year. It's calculated by averaging a student's grades, with each course module weighted equally based on its credit value (Cooper, 2018). GPAs are used to make decisions about a student's academic progress, eligibility for scholarships, and admission to advanced studies.

Teacher Ratings: This provides an overview of the Teacher Rating Scale (TRS), which is a tool for assessing a student's behavior and adaptive functioning in school. The TRS has separate forms for preschool, child, and adolescent age groups

Empirical Review

Itam, Abang, Eze, and Takon (2024) examined the relationship between educational technology and students' academic outcome at health training facilities in Nigeria's Cross River State. Five hypotheses were developed to direct the investigation in order to accomplish the goal. Accordingly, literature pertaining to the study's variables was evaluated. The study utilised survey design. Male and female students from five different health facilities in the state comprised the population. Sample comprised of three hundred (300) respondents, chosen through the accidental and random sampling procedures. The primary tool for gathering data was a questionnaire. Two specialists in measurement and evaluation from the Faculty of Education validate the data collection tool. Reliability was measured via the Cronbach Alpha reliability approach. The respondents were given three hundred (300) copies of the questionnaire in person. All distributed questionnaire were retrieved (100% return) successfully at the end of the exercise. Hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance using SPSS version 23. According to the findings, students' academic performance at health training institutes is greatly impacted by computer services, e-learning resources, and internet services. There were recommendations and ideas for additional research.

Nayak, Barik, and Bag (2024) examined how Blended Learning affected students in secondary school with regards to their academic performance in social science. Using a simple random sampling methodology, 40 ninth-grade students from the Govt. Secondary School in Baripada town, Mayurbhanj District (18 males and 22 females) were chosen as samples for the experimental research procedure. The researchers employed a self-made achievement test to gather data, and they used independent t-test, mean and standard deviation statistical techniques to analyse the data at significance levels of 0.01 and 0.05. The findings demonstrated a significant positive correlation between the impact of Blended Learning and the academic achievement of secondary school pupils in the Mayurbhanj District's Baripada town. The results also demonstrated that, when employing Blended Learning, there is no discernible difference in academic achievement between ninth-grade males and girls.

Olatunde-Aiyedun and Adams (2022) investigated how Blended Learning approaches affect students' retention and academic performance in science classes. Determining the feasibility of using a BL approach in science classes at the secondary school level was the aim of the current study. In order to undertake the current study project, a quasi-experimental approach was used. The study involved the recruitment of 120 undergraduate students from the Centre for Distance Learning and Continuous Education at the University of Abuja. Data was gathered using the Blended Learning model success test (BMAT) and the Blended Learning model retention test (BMRT). For eight weeks, the experimental groups' students received instruction utilising BL techniques. Six groups were given the pre-test, post-test I, and post-test II, which are the three tests. Version 23 of the SPSS was used to evaluate the hypotheses and respond to the research questions with mean score, standard variation, and error. The related samples t-test was used for inferential statistics at a significance level of 0.05. The mean pre- and post-test achievement and retention ability of children who were receiving science teaching through BL differed significantly, according to the results. The study found that BLMs greatly increase students' performance and retention in science. Because BL techniques enhance student retention and academic success, they are advised for use in scientific education.

Eunice and Linda (2023) carried out a study, educating university students on ICT as a sustainable developmental tool for Blended Learning. The University of Ibadan, Nigeria's Faculty of

Education provided a sample of undergraduate students for the study. Grounded on the goals of the research, a purposeful sample of students was chosen. It used a mixed-method survey design. A total of 117 students completed the online survey (quantitative component); while a focus group interview with 4 students (qualitative component) was conducted. The findings showed significant barriers to, and affordances of, the use of ICT as a blended-learning tool. In addition, the study discussed student access to ICT devices and internet facilities on campus, student proficiency in using these devices and facilities, and the impact these have on students' academic activities.

Ashibekong (2020) conducted research on the connection between students' academic achievement in business courses and information and communication technology facilities. This study's primary goal was to ascertain how ICTs are used as teaching tools in the Calabar Municipality of Cross River State to teach business studies. To direct the investigation, three hypotheses were developed. A total of 312 respondents were chosen using the simple random sample technique from a 3,237 population size of people, which included all JSS 3 students enrolled in public secondary schools in the Calabar Municipality. An academic performance exam and a questionnaire were used to collect primary data. Instrument administration was done by the researcher herself. The Pearson product moment correlation analysis method with 311 degrees of freedom and a 0.05 threshold of significance was used to examine the collected data. The results demonstrated that students' academic achievement in Business Studies was not significantly correlated with the availability and use of ICT facilities. However, it was discovered that students' academic achievement in Business Studies was significantly correlated with the functionality of ICT facilities. Among other things, the government should mandate that all students studying business studies have an understanding of ICT, according to the conclusions.

Agozi (2019) conducted a study on how Business Education students' academic performance at Rivers State universities is impacted by information and communication technologies. Investigating how information and communication technology is considered to affect Business Education students' academic performance is the aim of this study. Two hypotheses and two research questions were proposed to help with the investigation. From a population of 3200 students, 365 participants were chosen at random using Taro Yamen's approach. Z-test statistics were utilised in evaluating hypotheses at .05 level of significance. On the other hand, mean and standard deviation were utilised to address research questions.

According to the findings, students' academic performance is greatly impacted by information and communication technology (ICT) when they use it for individualised study and to find, learn, and update information. As a result, among other things, it was suggested that stakeholders and institutions should supply ICT resources for efficient Business Education instruction and that students be urged to use these resources. Hypotheses below were put forth in this study:

H₀₁: There is no significant correlation between ICT Blended Learning infrastructure and standardized test scores in Rivers State tertiary institutions.

H₀₂: There is no significant correlation between ICT Blended Learning infrastructure and grade point averages in Rivers State tertiary institutions.

H₀₃: There is no significant correlation between ICT Blended Learning infrastructure and teacher ratings in Rivers State tertiary institutions.

Methodology

This study used a correlational inquiry type and a descriptive research methodology. The three postsecondary educational establishments in Rivers State that provide Business Education programs— Federal College of Education, Omoku, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (AUE), and Rivers State University (RSU)—were the sites of this study. Undergraduate students enrolled in I 640 Business Education (RSU = 6140; AUE = 6140; FCET = 6140) made up the study's population. 614 students were chosen as respondents to partake in the study using a straightforward random sample procedure. To evaluate the hypotheses and determine the relationship between ICT Blended Learning infrastructure and Business Education students' academic performance, Pearson's Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) is utilised with the aid of SPSS) version 23.0.

Table 1: Reliability Test - Cronbach's Alpha Analysis

S/N	Variables	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha Coefficients
1	ICT Blended Learning Infrastructure	3	0.971
2	Standardized Test Scores	3	0.893
3	Grade Point Averages	3	0.963
4	Teacher Ratings	3	0.964

Source: SPSS Output form field data

As shown in Table 1, the results of the Cronbach’s alpha analysis showed that all the variables in the study produced high Cronbach’s Alpha coefficients indicating that, there is inter-item consistency among the variables in the study. This means that, if this study is conducted again in similar condition, the results would be similar to the results of our study.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of ICT Blended Learning infrastructure

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
To what extent do you learn with computers?	614	1	4	220	4.00	1.217	1.481
To what extent do you learn with network and internet?	614	1	4	214	3.89	1.242	1.443
To what extent do your teachers adopt display screen and peripherals for teaching and learning?	614	1	4	219	3.98	1.421	2.018
To what extent do you experience software and information system based teaching and learning?	614	1	4	230	4.18	1.321	1.744
Valid N (listwise)	614						

Source: Research Desk, 2024.

The high mean scores of the questionnaire items in Table 2 range above 3.00, indicating that a larger percentage of respondents expressed very high and high levels of acceptability of the study issue about ICT Blended Learning infrastructure. However, it is evident that question 4, which asked how much students at Rivers State tertiary institutions encounter teaching and learning through software and information systems, gets the highest mean score (4.18). This demonstrates how question 4 affects the variables the most.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Standardized Test Scores

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
To what extent does standardized testing affect students overall academic performance?	614	1	4	232	4.22	1.272	1.618
To what extent do you believe that standardized testing accurately reflects the quality of education in your school?	614	1	4	232	4.22	1.197	1.433
To what extent do you believe that standardized testing adequately prepares students for real-world challenges?	614	1	4	230	4.18	1.188	1.411
To what extent do you believe that standardized testing reflects my true academic abilities?	614	1	4	234	4.24	1.190	1.414
Valid N (listwise)	614						

Source: Research Desk, 2024.

With regard to standardised test scores, Table 3 shows that a higher percentage of participants demonstrated very high and high levels of acceptability to the study items, as indicated in the questionnaire items of high mean scores above 3.00. The highest mean score, 4.24, was found for question 4, which asked students at Rivers State tertiary institutions how much they thought standardised testing accurately represented their academic talents. This demonstrates that the question that affects the variables the most is question 4.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics of Grade Point Averages

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
Grading might be a pass, credit, high distinction, distinction and so on?	614	1	4	222	4.04	.860	.739
	614	1	4	220	4.00	.882	.778
The Grade Point Average (GPA) is an internationally recognised calculation used to find the average result of all grades achieved throughout your course?	614	1	4	229	4.16	1.214	1.473
Valid N (listwise)	614						

Source: Research Desk, 2024.

Given that the questionnaire items in Table 4 have high mean scores of more than 3.00, a larger percentage of respondents indicated very high and high levels of approval of the study topic in relation to grade point averages. It is evident, therefore, that question 4, which asked how much one believes that the GPA is a globally accepted formula that determines the average of all marks earned throughout a course, had the highest mean score, at 4.46. This indicates that the variable that has the biggest impact on the variables is question 4.

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics of Teacher Ratings

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
Our teachers rate our academic performance ?	614	1	4	224	4.07	1.244	1.6140
We are given home work after treating each topic?	614	1	4	231	4.20	.779	.607
We have periodic class tests?	614	1	4	223	4.04	.848	.719
We also write exams at the end of every semester?	614	1	4	233	4.24	1.122	1.248
Valid N (listwise)	614						

Source: Research Desk, 2024.

The high mean scores of the questionnaire items in Table 4 range over 3.00, indicating that a larger percentage of respondents showed very high and high levels of acceptability of the research issue in relation to teacher ratings. Nonetheless, it is evident that issue 4, which aimed to ascertain the degree to which students at Rivers State postsecondary institutions take tests at the conclusion of each semester, had the highest mean score (4.24). This demonstrates how question 4 affects the variables the most.

Bivariate Analysis

The PPMC tool was used to analyse the secondary data at a 94% confidence level. The experiments specifically address hypotheses Ho1 through Ho3. Since the analysis was conducted using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation, a significance level of 0.04 was chosen as the probability threshold for adopting the null hypotheses at $P > 0.04$ or, rejecting them at $P < 0.04$.

Ho1: There is no significant correlation between ICT Blended Learning infrastructure and standardized test scores in Rivers State tertiary institutions.

Table 6: Relationship between ICT Blended Learning Infrastructure and Standardized Test Scores

		ICT Blended Learning Infrastructure	Standardized Test Scores
ICT Blended Learning Infrastructure	Pearson Correlation	1	.733**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	614	614
Standardized Test Scores	Pearson Correlation	.733**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	614	614

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output, 2024.

Standardised test scores and ICT integrated learning infrastructure have a high and positive link, as evidenced by the correlation coefficient of 0.733** between the two, according to the SPSS output on Table 6. ICT integrated learning infrastructure and standardised test scores are significantly correlated, as evidenced by the probability value (0.000) being less than the critical threshold (0.04). This suggests that while externalities may be responsible for some of the variations in standardised test scores among Rivers State's postsecondary institutions, ICT Blended Learning infrastructure is primarily to blame. In light of this, we accept the alternative that there is a strong significant correlation between ICT Blended Learning infrastructure and standardised test scores in Rivers State tertiary institutions, rejecting the null hypothesis that there is no significant correlation between the two.

Ho₂: There is no significant correlation between ICT Blended Learning infrastructure and grade point averages in Rivers State tertiary institutions.

Table 7: Relationship between ICT Blended Learning Infrastructure and Grade Point Averages

		ICT Blended Learning Infrastructure	Grade Point Averages
ICT Blended Learning Infrastructure	Pearson Correlation	1	.820**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	614	614
Grade Point Averages	Pearson Correlation	.820**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	614	614

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output, 2024.

It is evident from the SPSS result on Table 7 that there is a very significant and positive association between grade point averages and ICT integrated learning infrastructure, with a correlation coefficient of 0.820**. Furthermore, the probability value (0.000) is lower than the crucial value (0.04), indicating a highly significant relationship between grade point averages and ICT integrated learning infrastructure. This suggests that ICT integrated learning infrastructure is responsible for the majority of grade point average changes among Rivers State's tertiary institutions, with externalities accounting for the remainder. Accordingly, we accept the alternative that there is a strong significant correlation between ICT Blended Learning infrastructure and grade point averages in Rivers State tertiary institutions and reject the null hypothesis that there is no significant correlation between the two.

H₀₃: There is no significant correlation between ICT Blended Learning infrastructure and teacher ratings in Rivers State tertiary institutions.

Table 8: Relationship between ICT Blended Learning Infrastructure and Teacher Ratings		ICT Blended Learning Infrastructure	Teacher Ratings
ICT Blended Learning Infrastructure	Pearson Correlation	1	.693**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	614	614
Teacher Ratings	Pearson Correlation	.693**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	614	614

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output, 2024.

It is evident from the SPSS result on Table 8 that there is a high and positive association between teacher ratings and ICT Blended Learning infrastructure, with a correlation coefficient of 0.693**. Furthermore, there is a strong and substantial association between teacher ratings and ICT Blended Learning infrastructure, as evidenced by the probability value (0.000) being less than the crucial value (0.04). This suggests that ICT integrated learning infrastructure is responsible for the majority of changes in teacher ratings across Rivers State's higher institutions, with externalities accounting for the remainder. In light of this, we accept the alternative that there is a strong significant correlation between ICT Blended Learning infrastructure and teacher ratings in Rivers State tertiary institutions, rejecting the null hypothesis that there is no significant correlation between the two.

Discussion of Findings

Analysis of this study provided 0.733** as the correlation coefficient between ICT Blended Learning infrastructure and standardized test scores, indicating a strong and positive relationship between ICT Blended Learning infrastructure and standardized test scores. Furthermore, the fact

that the critical value (0.04) is greater than the probability value (0.000) indicates a highly significant correlation between ICT Blended Learning infrastructure and standardized test scores. The results of analysis also showed a correlation coefficient of 0.820** between ICT Blended Learning infrastructure and grade point averages, representing a very strong and positive relationship between ICT Blended Learning infrastructure and grade point averages. Furthermore, 0.000 (probability value) is less than 0.04 (critical value), this provided sufficient evidence that there exists a very strong significant correlation between ICT Blended Learning infrastructure and grade point averages. Outcome of the analysis further revealed 0.693** as a correlation coefficient between ICT Blended Learning infrastructure and teacher ratings, indicating a strong and positive relationship between ICT Blended Learning infrastructure and teacher ratings. Furthermore, given that the critical value (0.04) is more than the probability value (0.000), there is a strong and substantial association between ICT Blended Learning infrastructure and teacher ratings.

These results support the empirical findings of Itam, Abang, Eze, and Takon (2024), who looked into the relationship between students' academic performance and instructional technology in health training institutes in Nigeria's Cross River State. According to the findings, students' academic performance at health training institutes is greatly impacted by computer services, e-learning resources, and internet services. There were recommendations and ideas for additional research. Nayak, Barik and Bag (2024) investigated the impact of Blended Learning on secondary school students' academic performance in social science, which is consistent with the outcomes of the current research. The findings demonstrated a significant positive correlation between academic achievement of secondary school students in Baripada town, Mayurbhanj District, and the impact of Blended Learning. Since Olatunde-Aiyedun and Adams (2022) examined the impact of Blended Learning methods on students' academic performance and retention in scientific education, the current study also borrows legitimacy from their work. Based on the results, BLMs greatly increase students' scientific achievement and retention. Ashibekong (2020) conducted research on the connection between students' academic performance in Business Studies and information and communication technology facilities, which is consistent with the results of the current study. However, it was shown that there is a substantial correlation between students' academic achievement in Business Studies and the functionality of ICT facilities. ICT has a substantial impact on students' academic outcome through individualised study and the use of ICT to find, learn, and bring up-to-date knowledge, according to Agozi (2019).

Conclusion

This study shows that ICT Blended Learning infrastructure has correlation with Business Education students' academic performance. This is evidenced by the strong correlational values gotten from analysis of data. Based on the study's findings and the degree to which they align with those of related earlier research, we draw the conclusion that ICT Blended Learning infrastructure significantly affects students' academic outcomes in Business Education in Rivers State postsecondary institutions. The academic performance of Business Education students has improved over time, and this is largely due to the ICT Blended Learning infrastructure, irrespective of the school organization and setting. Thus, adoption of ICT Blended Learning infrastructure will significantly improve the academic outcome of students of Business Education in Rivers State tertiary institutions.

Recommendations

Given the study's results and conclusion, as well as the fact that they are consistent with those of other research of a similar nature, we put forward the following recommendations:

1. Administrators of tertiary institutions in Rivers State should adopt ICT Blended Learning infrastructure as a strategy to enhance students' experience, as well as improve overall Business Education students' academic performance.
2. Administrators of higher institutions in Rivers State should also consider the strategic role of ICT Blended Learning infrastructure in their quest to understand the causes of students' performance, this would boost teacher ratings as well as improve overall performance.

References

- Agozi, V.A. (2019). Influence of information and communication technology on Business Education students' academic performance in universities in Rivers State. *Rivers State University Journal of Education*, 22 (1&2)
- Akude, I. (2014). *New technologies and innovative technologies in education*. Bomaway Publishers, Owerri.
- Ashibekong, F. (2020). Information and communication technology facilities and students' academic performance in business studies. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3962572>
- Bupo, G.O. & Ibeneme, O.T. (2020). Effect of Blended Learning approach on Business Education students' academic achievement in financial accounting in universities in Rivers State, Nigeria. *Journal of the Nigerian Academy of Education*, 16(1)
- Cooper, N. (2018). *Distance learning vs face-to-face - benefits and drawbacks*. Retrieved from <https://www.ncchomelearning.co.uk/blog/distance-learning-vs-face-to-face-benefits-and-drawbacks/>
- Eunice, K.A., & Linda, L. (2023). Information and communication technology as a blended-learning tool for sustainable development for university students. *International Journal of Sciences and Research*, 79(1)
- Hoyle, E. (2012). *Concept of academic performance and policies of school management*. Suffolk: The Press Ltd.
- Itam W.P., Abang M.O., Eze E.A., & Takon M, B, (2024) Educational Technology and Students Academic Performance in Health Training Institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Health and Psychology Research*, 12(1)58-103
- Makwasha, Lucia; Takavarasha, Sam Jnr; and Mubango, Hazel, "Blended Learning in the wake of ICT infrastructure deficiencies: The case of a Zimbabwean University" (2023). *African Conference on Information Systems and Technology*. 27. <https://digitalcommons.kennesaw.edu/acist/2023/presentations/27>
- Narad, A., & Abdullah, B. (2016). Academic performance of senior secondary school students: Influence of parental encouragement and school environment. *Rupkatha Journal on Interdisciplinary Studies in Humanities Special Issue*, 3(2), 12-19.
- Nayak, K., Barik, G., & Bag, S. (2024). Effect of Blended Learning on the academic achievement in social science of secondary school students. *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research (IJFMR)*, 6(1)
- Oladunjoye, T. G. (2016). Optimizing Business Education for national development. *Nigerian Journal of Business Education*, 3(1), 1-16.

- Olatunde-Aiyedun, T. G., & Adams, S. O. (2022). Effect of Blended Learning models on students' academic achievement and retention in science education. *Eurasian Journal of Science and Environmental Education*, 2(2), 35-42. <https://doi.org/10.30935/ejsee/12613>
- Osiki, J. O. (2001). Effects of remedial training programme on the management of learning acquisition defectiveness and poor study habits problems of selected subjects in a community grammar school. *Nigerian journal of applied psychology*, 6(2), 107-115.
- Vo, H. M., Zhu, C., & Diep, N. A. (2017). The effect of Blended Learning on student performance at course-level in higher education: A meta-analysis. *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, 53, 17- 28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stueduc.2017.01.002>
- Wosu, U. N. (2023). Effects of instructional strategies and gender on junior secondary school students' achievement in business studies in Rivers State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education Learning and Development*, 11(6), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.37745/ijeld.2013/vol11n6115>.